

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES IN THE PROFESSIONAL
ACTIVITY OF A MODERN TEACHER

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Abstract. The article is devoted to a detailed consideration of the issue integration of digital technologies and electronic educational resources into within the professional activities of teachers. This work presents data on the relationship between the stages of integration of digital technologies and electronic educational resources for full-time education in accordance with the levels of ICT competence of the teacher. Analyzed digital technologies that exist today, allowing teachers to improve their professional activities.

Keywords. digital technologies, ICT competence of a teacher, digital competencies, successful teaching activities, modern educational space, ICT competencies, school teacher.

Digitalization of education is the answer to the challenges of a developing modern society. This is due to the emergence of the digital economy and the transition of industry to a new technological structure. The development of digital technologies and the accumulation of digital resources today create the preconditions for the transformation of almost all types of human activity. Government services are provided in electronic formats, telemedicine is being developed based on remote interactions, and Internet users are given access to digitized cultural values. Certain production processes are moving into the digital environment, and the production of new high-tech products is being intensified and enriched. In this regard, the demands of the labor market and the requirements for the competencies of modern specialists are changing significantly. The processes of change in production are accelerating with the development and improvement of new technologies.

The digital environment opens up opportunities for continuous professional development for teachers with remote access to online courses, network seminars, digital educational resources, electronic libraries and scientific databases, including those in foreign languages. In a corporate environment, digital competencies allow teachers to modify and improve the effectiveness of organizational communication, which is important for enhancing the productivity of professional activities. In the context of digitalization of the environment, organizational communication is implemented through network interactions, in multimodal formats, in synchronous and asynchronous communication, with the accumulation of electronic discourse. This enhances professional cooperation, interactions with colleagues, parents, and the scientific community. Joint implementation of innovative projects - exchange of ideas and materials with other educational organizations, joint work with documents.

Today, the issue of ICT competence is becoming increasingly relevant. teacher, as the main and necessary aspect for the development of digital educational technologies and distance learning, which are now are popularized quite often.

Thus, a modern teacher must have the skills and skills that correspond to the subject-pedagogical level of ICT competence and allow him not only to apply digital technologies (DT), but also create and publish your own electronic educational resources (EOR).

Digital competencies of teachers should open up new opportunities for the development of students. Thus, in inclusive education, the creation of digital educational resources in multimedia formats makes it possible to recode information into different symbolic forms. Audiobooks are being created for the visually impaired. Visualization of educational materials and automatic recoding of oral speech into written text for hearing-impaired students. Special sensory gadgets are used for people with sensory perception problems. Accessibility and inclusiveness of learning is complemented by the possible differentiation and personalization of learning using innovative pedagogical strategies and practices in a digital environment. New approaches to learning using the potential of the digital environment make it possible to improve the learning process through the active involvement of students who are motivated to work with new tools and technologies. By organizing joint online learning activities, exchange of ideas, distribution of roles, discussions in online interactions, etc. Formation of student competencies. The digital competencies of a teacher, when using a digital educational environment, allow, along with information literacy, to also develop the digital literacy of schoolchildren, necessary for life and activity in the digital world. Digital literacy includes the skills of reliable information search on the Internet and its critical selection. Communication and collaboration in the digital environment, in terms of media literacy and netiquette skills. Ability to create digital content and ensure the security of personal data. Promoting responsible use of digital technologies and solving problems using digital technologies. Developing students' digital skills as 21st century skills should promote digital collaboration, security, and problem-solving abilities. Digital literacy includes the personal, technical and intellectual digital skills needed to live in a digital world. Thus, the formation of all aspects of the digital competencies of a modern teacher will help him confidently, effectively, safely, critically and creatively choose and use digital technologies in his professional activities. Conclusion Digitalization of education leads to transformation of the educational environment, new models of educational and training activities. With proper management of these processes, they accelerate the development of educational institutions and its employees. All this creates the prerequisites for new horizons for the development of students, increasing their self-realization in educational and future professional activities.

Let us turn to the structure of digital competencies for teachers recommended by UNESCO. The list of competencies consists of three modules:

- Application of ICT – preparing students to use digital technologies for social development.
- Mastering knowledge is the formation of students' abilities for the social and economic development of their country using digital technologies.
- Knowledge production is the development of students' abilities to reproduce acquired knowledge and participate in innovative processes.

Each of these modules includes six aspects of work: understanding the role of digital competencies in education, curriculum and assessment, teaching practices, ICT hardware and software, organization and management of the educational process, professional development.

Note that the classification of digital competencies of teachers contributes to the development of ICT competencies among students in the process of acquiring new knowledge, but does not describe the means, methods and methods of successful teaching activities of teaching staff.

Skillful use of digital competencies allows teachers to use system solutions in the digital environment in their professional activities: collections of educational materials, educational means of communication, means of managing the educational process, creative portfolios of students and skillful maintenance of electronic diaries.

The use of digital competencies also increases the teacher's competitiveness in a professional environment and focuses on developing in students the value of education and general media literacy when working with information on the Internet and global media.

It is worth noting that the capabilities of a digital school are aimed at transforming the educational system into a global digital civilization. It turns out that mastery of digital competencies is the basis for successful teaching activities aimed at improving the qualifications and competitiveness of teaching staff.

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